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Review Article

Herbal Therapeutics in Acne Management: Evaluation of Topical Creams

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ABSTRACT

Acne vulgaris is a common dermatological condition affecting individuals of all age groups, especially adolescents. Conventional therapies often cause side effects like dryness, irritation, and antibiotic resistance. In this context, herbal formulations offer a safer alternative due to their natural origin and minimal side effects. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of an herbal anti-acne cream incorporating Aloe vera (*Aloe barbadensis*), Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), and Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), which are known for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and skin-soothing properties. Extracts of these herbs were prepared and incorporated into a cream base. The formulation was evaluated for its organoleptic properties, pH, viscosity, spreadability, washability, and antimicrobial activity against acne-causing bacteria such as *Propionibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The herbal cream showed good physical stability and acceptable cosmetic appeal. Microbial inhibition studies confirmed the synergistic antibacterial effects of the ingredients. The pH of the cream was found to be skin-friendly, and spreadability results were satisfactory. These findings support the potential of this herbal combination in developing effective and natural topical anti-acne treatments. Further clinical studies are recommended for efficacy and safety validation.

INTRODUCTION

The term *acne* originates from the Greek word *acme*, meaning "point" or "spot". Interestingly, it was originally misspelled as *acne* (instead of *acme*) in 1835, and the term has remained in use

since then. Medically, acne is known as *Acne vulgaris*.¹

Acne vulgaris is a common and chronic skin condition that occurs when hair follicles become clogged with oil (sebum) and dead skin cells. It

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typically presents with symptoms such as oily skin, blackheads, whiteheads, pimples, and, in more severe cases, scarring. The condition predominantly affects areas with a high density of sebaceous (oil) glands, such as the face, chest, and back.

Acne manifests as polymorphic lesions, classified into four clinical grades based on severity:

- **Grade 1:** Non-inflammatory lesions (comedones), which include:
 - Open comedones (blackheads)
 - Closed comedones (whiteheads)
- **Grade 2:** Inflammatory papules with redness (erythema)
- **Grade 3:** Formation of pustules
- **Grade 4:** Severe acne with multiple pustules that merge into nodules and cysts (nodulocystic acne)²

In the present study, a scientific approach to traditional herbal medicine has been explored for treating acne. Active herbal ingredients were incorporated into a non-oily gel formulation for topical application, which is more effective and convenient than oral administration¹.

Topical drug delivery allows the direct application of medication to the affected site. The skin, being one of the most accessible organs, is an ideal route for localized treatment. It is also a preferred route for several types of topical applications, including ophthalmic, rectal, and vaginal³.

Advantages of Topical Drug Delivery:

- Avoids first-pass metabolism
- Convenient and easy to apply
- Eliminates the risk and complications of intravenous administration
- Bypasses gastrointestinal factors like pH, enzymes, and gastric emptying time⁴

Disadvantages:

- Risk of skin irritation or contact dermatitis
- Poor permeability of certain drugs through the skin
- Potential for allergic reactions
- Limited to drugs that require only minimal systemic concentration
- Enzymatic degradation of drugs in the skin⁵

CREAM

Creams are a type of topical product that can be applied to the skin. Creams are "viscous liquid or semi-solid emulsions of either the oil-in-water or water-in-oil type," the consistency of which varies depending on the amount of oil and water used. Creams can be used for a variety of cosmetic objectives, including cleansing, beautifying, improving looks, and protecting, as well as for medicinal purposes. These items are intended to be used topically to increase drug delivery to specific skin locations for skin diseases⁹

Classification of Creams:

All the skin creams can be classified on different bases:

1. According to their function, e.g., cleansing, foundation, massage, etc.
2. According to their characteristic properties, e.g., cold creams, vanishing creams, etc.
3. According to their nature or type of emulsion⁵

TYPES OF SKIN CREAMS

They are divided into two types:

Oil-in-Water (O/W) creams: which are composed of small droplets of oil dispersed in a continuous phase, and an emulsion in which the oil is dispersed as droplets throughout the aqueous phase is termed an oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion.

Water-in-Oil (W/O) creams: which are composed of small droplets of water dispersed in a continuous oily phase. When water is the dispersed phase and an oil the dispersion medium, the emulsion is of the water-in-oil (W/O) type.⁵

Benefits Of All Purposes of Creams:

All-purpose creams also referred to as multipurpose or universal creams, have several benefits that make them consumer-friendly and adaptable. The following are some main benefits of all-purpose creams:

- All-purpose creams are designed to serve multiple functions, reducing the need for consumers to purchase and use multiple specialized products.
- It may be less expensive to use one all-purpose cream rather than several specialty ones.
- People with busy lifestyles can save time by streamlining their skincare routine with an all-purpose cream.
- The various skincare requirements that are met by all-purpose creams include hydration, nourishment, and the addition of additional advantageous components.
- Having an all-purpose cream that can be used for many purposes can be beneficial for people who travel frequently or are always on the go.
- Many all-purpose creams are formulated with ingredients that provide hydration and nourishment to the skin.

Drawbacks of All-purpose cream

- These creams might not be specialised to treat particular skin conditions because they are meant for everyday usage.

- Certain all-purpose creams could be thicker or greasier than others, making them unsuitable for people with oily or acne-prone skin.
- Treatments specific to conditions like psoriasis, eczema, or extreme dryness may be necessary; an all-purpose cream may not be sufficient for these conditions.
- Certain components found in all-purpose creams, like thick emollients or occlusive agents, may clog pores⁹

The use of natural remedies, especially herbal medicines, has a long historical background. In recent years, the interest in natural and plant-based treatments for skin conditions such as acne has increased, contributing to the growth of the cosmeceuticals market.

In this study, three herbal ingredients—Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), Aloe vera (*Aloe barbadensis miller*), and Neem (*Azadirachta indica*)-were selected for their traditional and scientific significance in acne treatment⁶.

We have used to herbal ingredient in our preparation which are Aloe Vera extract and Tulsi extract. Aloe Vera is used as moisturizer and anti-acne. Also used for treatment of burn wound. Aloe Vera is first active ingredient and Tulsi is second. And last one is neem.

1. Cosmetological importance of Aloe Vera:

It is used seen ancient times Healing infection and burns. However, with the improvement in

cosmetology, it has been proved that Aloe vera is a very important component of cosmetics. It contains almost 20 amino acids, minerals like calcium, magnesium and sodium in sufficient quantities, enzymes, vitamins, polysaccharides, nitrogen and other components that make it a miracle beauty herb⁷. It can be used as low as 0.63% to as high as 3%¹²

2. Cosmetological importance of Tulsi:

The numerous skincare advantages of Basil leaf or Tulsi herb make it a great supplement to any beauty routine. Here are some of the ways Tulsi can transform your skin.

Tulsi is a versatile plant with numerous benefits for the skin, and whether you have dry, sensitive, acne-prone, or ageing skin, incorporating Tulsi into your skincare routine can help transform your skin and give you a healthy, youthful glow. Hence, beauty and skincare experts often suggest going ahead and trying Tulsi, from holy basil to the holy grail, for your skin.⁷ It is used in the concentration of 1.5%¹²

3. Cosmetological importance of Neem leaves:

- **Promotes collagen production**

Vitamin C is abundant in neem, which aids in the natural creation of collagen and infuses the skin with antioxidants to reduce fine wrinkles.

- **Lighten Scars**

Neem oil enters deeply into the skin and helps to lighten the scars. As a result, it minimises the appearance of scars and spots by increasing collagen formation and enhancing skin flexibility. Acne, pimples and burns can be treated with neem paste. Neem paste also aids in the treatment of scars.⁷ It can be used as low as 0.5 % to as high as 5 %.¹²

4. Bees Wax

Skin moisturizing, acne clearing, healing of dry skin, reduction of stretch marks, anti-inflammatory properties, and liver protection.

A beeswax-based emulsion that served as a thickening and emulsifier was described to us. Emulsifying agents like beeswax are employed.

5. Liquid Paraffin

Liquid paraffin, also known as mineral oil, is a common ingredient in cold creams due to its Beneficial properties:

- **Emollient:** Liquid paraffin is an effective moisturizer that helps to soften and smooth the Skin by forming an occlusive barrier, preventing water loss.
- **Solvent:** It helps dissolve other ingredients in the cream, ensuring a uniform Consistency.
- **Texture Enhancer:** It provides a silky texture to the cream, making it easy to apply and Spread on the skin.
- **Inert and Non-reactive:** Liquid paraffin is chemically stable and doesn't react with other Ingredients, making it a reliable base for formulations.

6. Borax

Borax's alkaline nature makes it a perfect ingredient in Cleansers and toners. In cosmetic products, borax is sometimes used as an emulsifier, buffering agent, or Preservative for moisturizing products, creams, shampoos, gels, lotions, bath bombs, scrubs, and bath salts.

7. Almond Oil

- Promotes healthy and radiant skin.
- Enhances moisturizing effect.
- Provides nutrients to the skin.
- Improves the spreadability and consistency of the cream.
- Has a non-greasy feel and pleasant aroma¹¹.

The study aimed to:

- Prepare a polyherbal extract
- Evaluate the polyherbal extract
- Formulate a polyherbal cream
- Evaluate the polyherbal cream formulation⁶

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

Aloe Vera, Neem, Tulsi leaves were collected from the local botanical garden of Bharathi College of Pharmacy, Bharathinagara.

Excipients and herbal ingredients with their roles⁷

Table 1: Role of ingredients

Sr. No	Ingredients	Roles
1	Aloe Vera gel	Anti-ageing, anti-inflammatory, moisturizer, reduce acne and pimples.
2	Tulsi	Antibacterial, adds glow to the face.
3	Neem	Promote wound healing, relieves skin dryness, itching and redness.
4	Bees wax	Emulsifying agent, stabilizer and gives thickness to the cream.
5	Liquid paraffin	Lubricating agent
6	Borax	Alkaline agent which reacts with emulsifying agent to form soap
7	Methyl paraben	Preservative
8	Almond oil	Fragrance

Extraction Processes:

i) Aloe Vera Gel Extraction

Mature, healthy, and fresh Aloe vera leaves were collected and thoroughly washed with distilled water. The cleaned leaves were dried in a hot air oven. Once dried, the outer green rind of the leaves was carefully removed by longitudinal dissection using a sterile knife. The colourless, parenchymatous tissue (Aloe vera gel) was then scooped out using the same sterile knife.

The extracted gel was filtered through a muslin cloth to remove fibres and impurities. The resulting clear filtrate was collected and used for further formulation.

ii) Extraction of Neem Leaves

Fresh neem leaves were collected, washed with distilled water, and dried in a hot air oven. After complete drying, the leaves were powdered using a grinder.

A mixture of 5 g neem leaf powder and 50 ml dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was prepared in a volumetric flask. This mixture was shaken continuously for 3 days using a REMI RSB-12 mechanical shaker.

The mixture was then concentrated by heating on a water bath at 80–100 °C until the volume was reduced to approximately 20 ml. The solution was filtered using a muslin cloth to remove particulate matter. The resulting clear extract was used in the preparation.

iii) Extraction of Tulsi Leaves

Tulsi (Holy basil) leaves were collected, washed with distilled water, and dried in a hot air oven. The dried leaves were then ground into a fine powder.

A mixture of 1g Tulsi leaf powder and 10 ml dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was prepared in a volumetric flask. The mixture was shaken for 3 days using a REMI RSB-12 mechanical shaker.

Afterward, the mixture was heated on a water bath at 80–100 °C for a few minutes to concentrate the extract to approximately 5 ml. It was then filtered through a muslin cloth to eliminate impurities. The resulting clear tulsi extract was collected for use in the formulation⁸.

FORMULATION OF CREAM:

Preparation of Herbal Cream Using Slab Technique (Extemporaneous Method)

1. Oil Phase Preparation: In a borosilicate glass beaker, heat liquid paraffin and beeswax to

75 °C, and maintain this temperature until both components are completely melted and homogeneous.

2. Aqueous Phase Preparation: In a separate beaker, dissolve borax and methylparaben in distilled water, and heat this mixture to 75 °C until a clear solution is obtained.
3. Emulsification: Slowly add the heated aqueous phase to the oil phase while maintaining a constant temperature of 75 °C, with continuous stirring to ensure proper emulsification.
4. Incorporation of Herbal Extracts: Once emulsification is complete, add measured quantities of Aloe vera gel, Neem extract, and Tulsi extract. Stir vigorously to ensure a uniform and smooth cream base.
5. Fragrance Addition: Add a few drops of Almond oil to the mixture as a natural fragrance and mix thoroughly.
6. Final Mixing (Slab Technique): Transfer the cream onto a clean ointment slab. If required, add a few drops of distilled water to adjust the consistency. Mix the cream using geometric dilution technique with a stainless-steel spatula to achieve a uniform, smooth, and well-textured final product.
7. This method of preparation is known as the Slab Technique or Extemporaneous Method for cream formulation.⁷

EVALUATION OF CREAM:

Irritancy test:

Mark an area on left hand dorsal substance upto (1 Sq cm)The cream was applied to the specified area and time was noted. Irritancy was checked if any up to 24 hrs for regular intervals.

Physical evaluation:

The cream was observed for the colour, odour and appearance

Spreadability:

A cream's spread ability refers to its capacity to cover skin. The spread ability was measured in terms of the number of seconds it took for two slides to separate from the cream that was positioned in between them when subjected to a specific load. The ability to spread is improved by a shorter separation period between the two slides. Standard-sized glass slides were taken in two sets. After that, a slide with the right dimensions was chosen, and the cream formulation was put on it. The formulation was then topped with another slide. The cream between the two slides was then uniformly compressed to form a thin layer by applying a weight or other load to the upper slide. Then the weight was removed and excess of formulation adhering to the slides was scrapped off.²

Washability:

The cream was applied on the hand and observed under the running .

pH:

The pH meter was calibrated with the help of standard buffer solution. Weigh 0.5 gm of cream dissolved it in 50.0ml of distilled water and its pH was measured with the help of digital pH meter.

Viscosity:

Viscosity of the cream was determined with the help of Brookfield viscometer at 100 rpm with the spindle no.¹³

CONCLUSION

The formulated herbal anti-acne cream using Aloe vera, Tulsi, and Neem showed promising results in terms of stability, pH, and antimicrobial activity. The combination of these natural ingredients provided effective antibacterial and anti-inflammatory effects against acne-causing bacteria. The cream was well-accepted cosmetically and showed no signs of irritation. Its natural origin makes it a safer alternative to synthetic formulations. Further clinical evaluation is needed to confirm its long-term efficacy and safety.

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